

Community-Based Acceleration Model of Entrepreneurship Growth and Development on Telematics Creative Industries in Malang Raya Indonesia

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Suggested Citation:

Supanto, F., Fristin, Y. 2017. Community-based acceleration model of entrepreneurship growth and development on telematics creative industries in Malang Raya Indonesia. *Journal of Applied Economic Sciences*, Volume XII, Winter 7(53): 2060-2072.

Abstract:

The current economic era has shifted from the information economy to the creative economy. The creative industry is one of the important contributors to the economies of countries in the world. The purpose of this research is to develop community-based acceleration model of entrepreneurship growth and development on Telematics Creative Industry (TCI) in Malang Raya. This is an exploratory research. The subjects of the research are communities and actors on telematics, local government organizations, business/industry, and academics. Data collection techniques used interview, Focus Group Discussion, Direct Observation and Documentation. Research data was analyzed by using qualitative descriptive analysis, SWOT analysis, and Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). The research concludes that the model that can be developed to increase the role of creative industry is Quadruple Helix model with optimization of each party's role to achieve synergy. Coordination is important for each region and among stakeholders. To improve the development of entrepreneurship in the field of Telematics Creative Industry in Malang Raya needs real actions from various parties, especially in the form of training, mentoring, facilitation and assistance.

Keywords: acceleration model; entrepreneurship; creative industries of telematics; Indonesia

JEL Classification: L26; F63; M13

Introduction

The creative industry is one of the important contributors to the economies of countries in the world. This evidence began from England in 1997 in which the development of its creative industry has driven a significant contribution from the industry to the state economy beyond the contribution of other conventional industries. Britain's success in developing its creative industry has been a driving force for similar efforts in other countries such as New Zealand, Norway, Sweden, Singapore, etc.

In Indonesia, the creative industry becomes a new economic power with its significant contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP). By 2015, the contribution of the creative industry to GDP is about 7.5% and is predicted to increase to 8% by 2016 (Wicaksono 2015). The creative economy is also proven to contribute to the employment of 10.65% of the total national workforce (Ariyanti 2015).

Government of East Java in order to develop the growth of new entrepreneurs engaged in the creative industry to formulate the Grand Strategy which since 2010 have been directed every development programs towards the realization of the East Java region as: "the leading center of the development of creative industries electronics and telematics, competitive, and sustainable towards an increasingly prosperous East Java". The growth potential of the electronics and telecommunications industries in East Java is also very high and is expected to continue to grow over the long term. The community's need for the telematics industry and its derivatives is increasing in line with the development of investment, technology and management. All these things are needed as a primary need, not just a mere lifestyle. This is also supported by the growing population of East Java, thus

forming a potential market for electronics and telematics products. East Java is also one of the provinces that occupy the top three national GDP (Strategic Plan of Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, 2012). The high PDRB is related to the purchasing power of creative industry products.

Nevertheless, the development of creative industries in East Java as in Indonesia generally faces various obstacles: (1) The development of creative industries that have not been optimum due to industry attractiveness factor, the dominant position of creative business, creative industry business model, and business risk to be faced; (2) The development of creative content, creation and technology has not been optimum due to inadequate internet infrastructure, performance building infrastructure has not met the standards, expensive production machines, expensive software product and creative services, lack of content research, lack of content archiving activity; (3) Lack of market expansion and penetration for creative products and services at home and abroad due to lack of appreciation of local creativity, lack of national distribution channels connectivity, overseas market concentration, high promotion costs, lack of online payment system, low monitoring royalties, licenses, copyrights; (4) Weak creative industry institutions due to factors; (5) lack of access to financing of players in the creative economy sector; (6) The development of creative economic resources is not optimal because of the low utilization of natural resources and the low utilization of human resources (2012-2014 Strategic Plan of Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, 2012).

Malang is one of the important cities for the development of creative industries both in East Java and national level. The development of creative industries in Malang is also growing very rapidly. In 2016, Malang became the center of the 2016 Indonesia Creative Cities Conference (ICCC) event which became the gathering place for creative economic entrepreneurs from all regions in Indonesia.

It is important to make efforts to develop the creative industries so that the goals set can be fulfilled. This research is intended to fill the gap by focusing on the preparation of acceleration model to cultivate and develop entrepreneurship in the creative industries of telematics in Malang Raya (Malang City, Malang Regency, and Batu City). The purpose of this study is to develop a community-based acceleration model of entrepreneurship growth and development in the Creative Industry of Telematics in Malang Raya.

1. Literature review

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship defined by Jong and Wennekers (2008) as taking risks to run your own business by exploiting opportunities to create new business or innovative approaches so that managed businesses grow bigger and more independent in facing the competitive challenges. Hisrich & Peters (2002) defines entrepreneurship as a process of creating something new by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the financial, psychological, and social risks that accompany it, and receiving the resulting rewards of personal and monetary satisfaction and freedom.

Creativity and innovative factors are the main elements in entrepreneurship. Creativity refers to the ability to develop new ideas and to discover new ways of solving problems in facing opportunities. While innovation is the ability to apply creativity in order to solve problems and opportunities to enhance and enrich life (Suryana 2003).

Creative Industry

In Indonesia, the creative industry is an industry sector which is part of the activities of the creative economy subsector. The creative economy is an economic activity that encompasses the industry with the creativity of human resources as the main asset to create economic added value based on 14 economic sub-sectors. In the Indonesian Creative Economy Development 2025 (Ministry of Trade of RI, 2008) mentioned that creative economy is a field of economic activity that focuses on the creation of goods and services by relying on expertise, talent and creativity as intellectual property. While the Creative Industry is an industry derived from the utilization of creativity, skills and individual talents to create welfare and employment by generating and exploiting the creative and creative power of the individual (Tourism Ministry Strategic Plan, 2012).

Based on the Presidential Instruction of the Republic of Indonesia No.6/2009 on Creative Economy Development, it is mentioned that the scope of Creative Economic Development includes: Advertising; Architecture;

The art and antiques market; Craft; Design; Fashion (fashion); Film, video, and photography; Interactive games; Music; Performing Arts; Publishing and printing; Computer and software services; Radio and television; Research and development.

Creative Industry of Telematics

The term Telematics stands for Telecommunication and Informatics. Telematics means a combination of communication network system with information technology. Telematics is a remote communications technology, which conveys one-way, as well as reciprocal, information with a digital system. Understanding Telematics itself refers more to the industry associated with the use of computers in telecommunications systems (Taimiyyah, 2014). Telematics is a new hybrid technology that emerged as the impact of the development of digital technology. Telematics today is also called Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

The telematics industry in Indonesia has actually emerged and developed since the late 1970s. The era was called a pilot period until the late 1980s. The next period is the introduction period beginning in the 1990s. Currently the period of Indonesian telematics industry development is in the period of application that began in the 2000s.

Figure 1. Development of community-based creative industry of telematics

Source: Indonesia Ministry of Trade (2008)

The pilot period is marked by the commencement of learning and the use of information technology, telecommunications, and multimedia. Telephone networks, national television channels, national and international radio stations, and computers are becoming known in Indonesia, but their use is limited. In the Introduction Period, telematics technology has been used more and more widely known to the public. Amateur radio networks are growing, even reaching abroad as a result of the creativity of young people at the time. In the Application Period, the Indonesian government is seriously responding to the development of telematics in the form of political decisions and policies through regulations that encourage the development of telematics, especially in relation to the development of creative economy.

The National Information Technology Framework (KTIN 2000) formulates the vision of developing national information technology, namely the realization of a competitive civil society based on information technology in 2020, in support of the unitary state of the Republic of Indonesia. To support the achievement of the vision, the

following strategic sectors are defined: E-government for good governance; E-business to support people's economy; Community-based IT; IT for education; and E-Democracy.

Based on this, it can be seen that the development of community-based telematics or community become one of the strategic sectors to achieve the vision of national information technology development. Community-based IT/Community development strategies include: (1) Provision of information access and information applications for the general public in all district and sub-district capitals; (2) Provision of funds and government investment programs that encourage and empower communities to utilize IT; (3) Achievement of the acculturation process to become a society that can utilize information technology; (4) Promotion and improvement of IT research, oriented to market needs and IT activities in the community.

The national creative economy development model is shown in Figure 2. Based on the Figure 2, it can be seen that the foundation of creative industry is the human resource (People) of Indonesia which is the most important element in the creative industry. As a pillar of creative economic development is industry, technology, resources, institution, and financial intermediary. The main actors of creative economic development are intellectuals (scholars), business and government.

Figure 2. Model of creative economy development

Source: Ministry of Trade, Republic of Indonesia (2008)

2. Methodology

This type of research is exploratory research using Mix Method approach. The research is exploratory to reveal various factors related to the potential for accelerated growth and entrepreneurship development in Telematics Creative Industry in Malang Raya, opportunities and constraints faced, and models for its development. The research is conducted in Malang Raya (Malang City, Malang Regency, Batu City). The subjects of research are: (1) Communities and players in Creative Industry of telematics; (2) Regional Working Unit (SKPD); (3) Business Community; (4) Academics. Data collection techniques use Interview, Focus Group Discussion, Direct Observation and Documentation. Data analysis using qualitative descriptive analysis techniques, SWOT and Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP).

3. Results and Discussion

Creative Industry of Telematics in Malang Raya

The holding of the Indonesia Creative City Conference 2016 (ICCC) event held in Malang on March 30-April 2 marked the momentum of the seriousness of the government and creative industry of telematics players in Malang

as well as various other related parties to jointly work together in advancing the creative industries in Malang. In the event the city of Malang declared itself as a creative city that focuses on telecommunications and informatics, especially digital animation.

To support these developments, the government of Malang has taken various strategic steps. One of them is the establishment of ILMETA and IATT Industry Sector in the Industry Department which there is a special section in charge of the development and development of Electronic Industry and IATT (Transportation and Telematics Equipment Industry). The commitment of Malang City Government is also shown through one of the missions of the Industry Service "Improving the Performance of Trade Sector and Creative Economy through the Facilitation of Promotion and Improvement of Trade Business Climate". Various events and activities have been conducted by Industrial services of Malang in order to foster and develop the telematics industry. Some of them are Mbois Festival, 3D Prototype Training, Android Application Development Training, Facilitation of Malang Animation Forum in INAFAC 2016, Digital Music Workshop, Graphic Design Workshop, Workshop Exhibition and Creative Industries Potential, and many other activities.

The Government of Malang City in 2015 has also built Technopark. Technopark is a gathering place for digital industry communities in Malang to develop their work in order to face the ASEAN Economic Community (MEA). This facility is located in the area of Public Library and Archive Building Office of Malang City.

Another strategic step is to establish Malang Creative Fusion (MCF). MCF community is expected to be a forum for sharing experiences, information, and the development of creative economic potential. Malang City Government is keen to make Malang as creative city in a sustainable manner. Therefore, the city government strongly supports the growth of creative industries of telematics in Malang, such as animation, graphic design, music, *etc.*

MCF in its effort to develop creative industry in Malang City using Quadro Helix Strategy, which is development creative industry involving government, academic, business and community. The synergy efforts are carried out by the MCF Synergy Team. Meanwhile, in an effort to help increase the marketing capacity of Malang creative industry product and service both national and international market, hence formed Creative Industrial Cooperative of Malang (KIKM). KIKM has programs such as providing facilities and medium for consultation, incubation, training on marketing skill improvement of Malang creative industry. KIKM also provides promotional and marketing facilities for Malang creative industries in the form of Creative Products Gallery of Malang, Export Trade House and Exhibition Activities both local, national and international.

In recent years, the development of Telematic Creative Industry in Malang City is moving rapidly. The fields of telematics that many cultivated by creative industry players are animation, film and videography, illustration and graphic design, photography, and so on. Statistics of MCF show that telematics industry is the most developed industry compared to other creative industries (Figure 3).

One that is growing rapidly is digital animation. The start-up growth of this business and the level of productivity are quite encouraging. It is estimated that there are more than 1000 animators in Malang with an average animation production of 400 animations per month (Jatmiko 2016).

Figure 3. Statistics of creative industry in malang

Source: MCF and Industrial Services of Malang (2017)

There are several factors supporting the development of Telematic Creative Industry in Malang. First, government support both the Government of East Java Province and Malang City Government. East Java Provincial Government established a forum for creative community of Jawa Timur Information Technology Creative (JITC Malang). JITC as an Information and Communication Technology Entrepreneur Incubator Institution in Malang City has been successfully implemented various non-commercial work programs established on March 11, 2013 by accommodating communities with expertise in Videography and Film, Photography, Web Design and Development, Animation, Digital Music and Interactive Games. JITC Malang able to cultivate entrepreneurship of telematics industry especially community of creative beginner industry where overall development there are 132 volunteers divided in each sub area in year 2016. That number increased by 7 volunteers from 2015. The spread of volunteer number is quite varied based on expertise of each volunteer according to its sub-field, where sub field of animation have the most volunteer that is 43 volunteer. The second largest number of volunteers is the Videography and Film sub-section where there are 38 volunteers. Next is a sub field of photography with a total of 25 volunteers. The field of Web and Development number of volunteers increased to 9 people followed by Digital Audio field with the number of volunteers 8 people. Interactive Game field is still the number of volunteers from the year 2015 is 5 people. And the new-born field in 2016 is Digital Illustration Field with the number of volunteers 4 people. The number of volunteers who continue to increase from year to year shows that JITC continues to grow and become known by the community so that it becomes a place for people who have expertise in the field of telematics in Malang Raya and the community has an obligation to form a network of inter-community creative industries telematics industry as well as developing new incubators for the already established community for new industrial communities in their respective regions (Trade and industry offices of East Java, 2016). The Government of Malang City showed great support towards the development of creative industries of telematics. Visible serious efforts of Malang City Government to make Malang as a city that supportive and comfortable for the development of telematics industry.

The second factor is educated, skilled and innovative human resources. Malang is a city of education with many universities. According to Fahmi, Head of ILMETA and IATT Department of Industry of Malang City, many of Telematic Creative Industry in Malang start from 23 universities both public and private that have a telematics-

based program so that many gathered human resources (students) who have telematics skills reliable. Similarly, in secondary education, there are many vocational high schools in Malang Raya. Even the number of vocational secondary schools in Malang Regency (122 schools) is the second largest in East Java after Jember (161 schools) (East Java Province in Figures, 2016). Some Vocational High Schools in Malang have majoring in telematics.

The third factor is the growth and development of creative communities. The Creative Industries of Telematics actors have formed many communities according to their own interests and business focus. The community becomes a medium of communication and sharing experiences for member development.

Fourth factor, support from business/industry. Many companies also support the development of Telematic Creative Industry in Malang in various forms. For example, PT Telkom established Malang Digital Lounge (DiLo) which provides various facilities and facilities for telematics creative community event in Malang. BRI also contributed by establishing Creative House.

Fifth factor, the contribution of universities to the Telematic Creative Industry in Malang City, especially in providing education and training of telematics, telematics research, and technical assistance.

Contribution of Telematics Creative Industry to Malang city economy began to be taken into account by the government. Unfortunately, at this time is not known accurately how much contribution Telematics Creative Industry to the economy of Malang. Some factors causing it, as told by Fahmi (Head of ILMETA and IATT Department of Industry of Malang City), among others is the first, sub-field of Creative Telematics Industry in the measurement of the Central Bureau of Statistics is still spread into various sectors so that Telematics Creative Industry specific data is hard to be identified. Secondly, because of the nature of their business, most of the Creative Industry Telematics actors still enter the criteria of the informal sector and do not register their business officially to the government so that the number is not known with certainty. As a result, the government can not accurately measure the economic potential, business variation, productivity, location distribution, contribution to taxes, labor absorption, and other indicators.

Unlike the city of Malang, the development of Creative Telematics Industry in Batu City has not been detected by Batu City Government. According to Evi (Head of IKM SMEs, SMEs Industrial Service of Batu City) and Danang (Section Head of SMEs, UKM Industrial Service of Batu City) it is because the focus of industrial development in Batu City still in some creative industries besides telematics, namely batik, culinary and typical souvenir of Batu City. As a result, the Creative Telematics Industry in Batu is less developed as in Malang City due to lack of attention from Batu City Government. The Creative Industrial Community of Telematics in Batu is also not sustainable so that many actors of the Telematics Creative Industry in Batu establish communication and develop their community by collaborating with the communities of telematics creative industry in Malang.

The development of telematics creative industry in Malang Regency is also similar as in Batu. The development has not been detected by the local government. Unlike the city of Batu, Malang Regency Government has just begun seriously try to foster and develop the telematics creative industry in its territory in 2017, despite various obstacles. According to Indra Anggraeni (Section Head of IATT - Industrial of Transportation and Telematics Equipment), the main obstacle of the development of telematics creative industry in Malang Regency is the difficulty to identify the potentials and players of telematics creative industry in Malang Regency. As the city of Batu, as a result of the lack of attention from the local government on the creative industries of telematics, many creative resources in the region are choosing to migrate to Malang.

The creative industry of telematics in Malang City has been much developed to focus on telematics content. Unlike the phenomenon in the city of Malang, the City of Batu and Malang Regency is still developing as a tool or means to promote and market products of SMEs in the region. Coaching has been done to many actors of SMEs from various products, not the creative industries of telematics itself, where content is the main product. Thus the aspect of telematics content has not been so developed.

Supporting factors and constraints

Some of the factors supporting the development of TCI in Malang Raya are: (1) Efforts in TCI can run efficiently because the nature of the product (digital) does not require high investment, especially in the place of production and storage; (2) Strong government support for TCI development especially in Malang; (3) The market of open

telematics products is vast, not only domestically but worldwide; (4) Availability of educated, skilled and experienced human resources in the field of TCI. This is supported by the many colleges and vocational schools that have ICT-based courses to produce graduates of highly qualified telematics skills; (5) Telematics devices with better availability and affordability. The WTO agreement on telematics devices causes telematics product entry tariffs to be zero percent. Thus, TCI actors in Indonesia will be more efficient; (6) Business support is good enough for TCI in Malang Raya; (7) The support of universities is good enough, especially through workshops / training, research activities and community services directed at TCI, technical assistance, and so on; (8) There are business incubators ready to assist business start-up in the field of TCI; (9) Live, solid, and active TCI communities in coaching both community members and the wider community; (10) The number of companies both private and state-owned enterprises that actively participate in supporting TCI development in Malang is still open for improvement.

Several factors hindering TCI development in Malang Raya are as follows: (1) The development of TCI is still focused in Malang City, while in Batu and Malang Regency runs slowly; (2) Content has not been the main product of TCI in Batu and Malang Regency, but still limited to become media to support the marketing of regional products; (3) Many TCI businesses in Malang Raya face capital difficulties to develop the business; (4) The migration of human resources qualified telematics from Batu and Malang Regency to Malang City as an impact of the attractiveness of Malang which is considered convenient for TCI. As a result, Batu and Malang Regency lack potential human resources for the development of TCI in the region; (5) Government support has not been strong enough in Batu and Malang Regency. Government of Batu currently focuses more on developing the creative industries of food and beverages and batik than TCI. Meanwhile, the new Malang regency government this year (2017) started to identify and map the actors of TCI in Malang Regency; (6) The tax regulation is deemed not to favor the micro and small scale creative efforts in the field of telematics, especially the newly developing ones; (7) Public appreciation of TCI is still low; (8) The contribution of TCI to regional development (economy, employment, poverty, etc.) has not been accurately measured. The industry classification in the measurement conducted by BPS does not contain the creative industries in particular.

Community-Based Model of Telematics Creative Industry Development in Malang Raya

Based on the analysis of characteristics, supporting factors and obstacles in TCI development in Malang Raya, a model for accelerated growth and entrepreneurship development in the community-based Telematics Creative Industry in Malang Raya. The model is shown in Figure 4.

Model that can be developed to enhance the role of the creative industry is the Quadruple Helix model. Quadruple helix is a framework that integrates relevant public investment and the importance of completeness between economic differences, expensive investment and policies to achieve economic growth balance and is a collaboration of four sectors: Government, business, Academia and Civil society (Oscar 2010).

Quadruple Helix concept is a development of Triple Helix by integrating civil society (Afonso 2012). The close relationship, mutual support and mutualism symbiosis between the four actors is expected to be the driving force for the growth of sustainable creative industries. The role of intellectuals in the context of the creative industry is the desire to apply science and spread it. Scholars include culturalists, artists, educators at educational institutions, pioneers in community (paguyuban), hermitage (padepokan), cultural and art studios, individual or group studies and researchers, writers, and other figures in the arts, culture and science. The determinants of small business success are the structural factors in meeting the benefits and location and the uniqueness of the business (Chawla 2010).

Figure 4. Community-based acceleration model of entrepreneurship growth and development

The role of a business/company is as an organizational entity created to provide goods or services to consumers. Businesses are generally privately owned and formed to generate profits and increase prosperity for their owners, and can be shaped through sole proprietorships, partnerships, corporations and cooperatives. The role of government is as an institution that has the authority of creative industry development, both by central and local government, as well as interrelationship in substance as well as administrative interconnection. Synergy between departments and agencies in the central government, synergy between central and local government is needed to achieve the vision, mission and target of creative industry development.

Campuses have a great capacity to encourage the growth of creativity, and mature the concept of innovation and have the capacity to disseminate information with business networks. Intellectuals have the role of an agent that disseminates science, art and technology as well as agents who can develop creative industries in society.

The research results of the academics can be applied to the development of ideas or ideas for the creative industry players and business management development, and academics can implement their activities through continuous assistance for the improvement of management for creative industry players. Academics is one of the drivers of the birth of creativity, ideas, science and technology for the growth of creative industries, so that will produce a creative industry that stands firmly.

The role of the Government in fostering creativity of creative industry players is quite good, namely as an institution that has the authority to create and apply laws and laws, both central government and local government. The role in encouraging innovation for TCI development has not met their expectations. Therefore, the synergy between local government (Provincial and District/City) can be implemented to synchronize the program so that it will not run partially and overlapping either in the form of regulation or facilitation for community and TCI actors is very much needed to reach the vision, mission and target of TCI development.

The role of established business actors is as business actors, investors, creators of new technology and consumers as well as On the Job Training or apprenticeship for TCI beginner business actors in the hope of supporting the continuity of TCI and as a place of learning for start up business. The role can be realized in the form of creators of creative products and services, new markets that can absorb product and services generated, and create jobs for creative individuals, create community and creative entrepreneurs, namely as a driver of the formation of public space, so that will happen sharing thinking, which can hone the creativity of industry players. The establishment of the business community will be able to change the mind-set of creative industry business actors as well as sharing management of business management that leads to innovations in various fields that are able to support the development of creative industries.

Creative community has a role, among others, to build capacity, internalize the character of entrepreneurship in business start-up, as a place to consult as well as make it as a media problem solving related problems encountered.

The role of business incubators is to nurture and assist new companies, helping them survive and grow in the start-up period during these vulnerable times. The ICT incubator of the model has a role as a community-based TCI development and strengthening consultant in various aspects: management, production, market and marketing and even facilitation in connecting TCI actors to financial institutions both banks and non-banks through various programs implemented to the community and the actors of TCI start recruitment, training, apprenticeship and mentoring to prepare the creative industry players from the informal sector to the formal sector and strengthen the creative industry players who have legal entities to further develop.

The role of creative industry players as subjects in this model can directly get facilitation, facilitation and consultation as well as market access and capital from other stakeholders such as Higher Education Institution, BUMN/BUMD and Business Actors that have been established to develop the industry. In addition, consultation, assistance, facilitation and market access as well as capital through a community that is formed both from universities through the implementation of Higher Education Tri Dharma or through Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) program. In the case of obtaining human resources as input in the process of entrepreneurial internalization sustainable then the source of input can come from the general public who are interested and have the required skills, vocational schools based on telematics and universities.

The role of Financial Institution (Banking) for Indonesian creative people is still low. Enterprises in the field of new creative industries based on digital content are still difficult to obtain financing support from financial institutions. This is because financial institutions do not understand the business nature in the creative industries, especially those based on this telematics. There is now a business credit financing scheme (KUR) launched by the President on November 5, 2007 based on a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between the Government, Guarantee Company and Banking (Bank Mandiri, BNI, BTN, BRI, Bank Bukopin, and Bank Syariah Mandiri) which may be utilized by the financing scheme for the creative industry. But this has not been able to be utilized by TCI due to the difference in business pattern of TCI sector in other industrial sectors, so banks tend to assess the creative industry sector has not been bankable. Therefore, it is necessary to create a policy or form of financing scheme appropriate for this TCI.

The position of BUMN / BUMD / BUMS institutions as facilitators who have the authority to provide program buffer facilities, so as to accelerate the process of achieving development targets related to the development of TCI based on the community. Various programs are activated by a well-established and strong business community, namely through CSR program.

The role of actors of similar industries and other industry actors as well as consumers is as a market of products and services produced by other industry actors. This is because the marketing of TCI products requires special attention, in addition, the design practice of marketing strategy of creative industry products requires its own creativity.

Strategy, Policy and Program of TCI Growth and Development in Malang Raya

The incubator is a place or environment or institutional system, with certain conditions deliberately made in such a way that anything placed in the incubator will experience better growth (Kadarisman 1997). Potentially and actual, industrial area elements have ICT incubators that are expected to increase acceleration, accessibility and affordability of technology transfer process, diffusion of innovation, technology adaptation that closer product research and technology produced and indeed real needed by industry players. The incubator institution is an alternative to bridge the needs of the perpetrator to flow the information flow and the results of the study in accordance with real and perceived needs as well as market value, as well as to establish a synergistic collaborative relationship with the research resources institution.

ICT Incubator performs a real needs analysis of the targeted or potential clients whose clients are through gathering and filtering information about the needs or presenting the various findings and results available to the tenants with their specifications in accordance with the abilities and capacity of the targeted actors. Based on the analysis of needs obtained from industry players, then further determine the pattern of interventions that can be done to solve the problem of meeting the needs of tenants. Interventions that can be done by ICT incubators are through capacity building, creative industry strengthening and institutional capacity building.

Policy Priorities of TCI Development in Malang Raya

Exploration of the development of TCI in Malang Raya both to the government, TCI actors, and the community of telematics to produce some policy recommendations and programs. The policies and programs are then analyzed using Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP).

Policies that can be taken by local government in Malang Raya are supporting, encouraging, and increasing the role of telematics community in: (1) Increasing motivation and entrepreneurship ability, especially among youth; (2) Improving capability in accessing capital and managing finances; (3) Improving ability in production process; (4) Improving ability in telematics product marketing; (5) Increase knowledge and ability in fulfilling aspect of business regulation, either licensing or protection of intellectual property rights.

Table 1 Program priority based on Analytical Hierarchy Process analysis

Alternatives	TOTAL	Normal	Ideal	Ranking
Aid	0.0755	0.151	0.3654	4
Facilitation	0.0983	0.1966	0.4757	3
Training	0.2067	0.4133	1	1
Mentoring	0.1195	0.239	0.5782	2

Source: AHP analysis results

Based on the AHP analysis of several criteria for the policy of growth and development of entrepreneurship TCI mentioned above, the sequence of program priorities that can be taken is as shown in Table 1.

The priority sequence of the TCI entrepreneurship growth and development program in Malang Raya is training, mentoring, facilitation and assistance. Training is very important to do specially to improve both hard skill and soft skill. Mentoring from various parties, whether government, academia, private, especially the community is needed so that the difficulties and obstacles faced by the new business does not kill the business. Facilitation is

expected by business actors in the field of TCI. Facilitation here means giving ease to the creative business of telematics to have access to various facilities that require a very long time to be fulfilled by themselves or even cannot be their own effort. Assistance is the last priority that can be done by stakeholders to develop entrepreneurship in the field of creative industries of telematics.

Conclusion

The research has resulted in the following conclusions: (1) Malang Raya has great potential for the development of Telematics Creative Industry due to government, private, intellectual and community support, broad market, the number of educated and skilled human resources, affordability of telematics equipment, business incubators; (2) Obstacles to the community-based growth and development of telematics creative industries in Malang Raya is the spread of uneven distribution of TCI, content has not become the main product of TCI in Batu and Malang Regency, capital difficulties, qualified telematics human resources migration from Batu and Malang Regency to Malang City, government support is not strong enough in Batu and Malang Regency, taxation regulation is considered not favored micro and small scale creative effort in telematics field, public awareness of TCI is still low, TCI contribution to regional development yet accurately measured; (3) A model that can be developed to enhance the role of the creative industry is the Quadruple Helix model by optimizing the roles of each party in synergy.

Based on these conclusions, the researchers recommend to the local government of Batu and Malang Regency to give more attention to Telematics Creative Industry in its territory so as not to be left behind by Malang City. Coordination is important for each region and among stakeholders to generate synergy. To improve the development of entrepreneurship in the field of Creative Telematics Industry in Malang Raya need concrete actions from various parties especially in the form of training, facilitation, facilitation and assistance.

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